

Bioimpedance-based tissue characterization for the detection of upper aero-digestive tract cancers

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INTRODUCTION

Cancers of the upper aero-digestive tract (UADT) represent approximately 8% of global cancer diagnoses [1], with around 500,000 deaths yearly. This pathology includes a heterogeneous group of malignancies arising from various anatomical subsites, with the oral cavity and larynx being the most affected, mainly by squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). Early detection of UADT cancers is crucial for effective treatment, leading to survival rates as high as 95%, while delayed diagnoses significantly increase the risk of metastasis, reducing the survival to around 20%. Recent studies [2][3][4] have shown that malignant tissues exhibit distinct electrical properties compared to healthy tissues. This has led to the development of innovative sensing devices based on Electrical Bioimpedance (EBI) of tissues as a faster, cost-effective and less invasive alternative to traditional cancer detection methods [5]. While previous research has mainly focused on demonstrating those differences, the present work aims to go further by analyzing EBI data and extracting meaningful features across multiple excitation frequencies. These metrics are then used to explore different classification approaches, with the goal of developing a comprehensive algorithm for accurate identification and staging of UADT cancers that could be later integrated into clinical tools and used during routine check-ups.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mucous laryngeal tissue samples from 17 patients undergoing oncological surgery at the Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery Unit of San Martino Polyclinic Hospital (Genoa, Italy) were analyzed using the SmartProbe system [6]. SmartProbe is a needle-based bipolar bioimpedance sensing system designed to investigate the electrical properties of biological tissues. It uses a concentric needle electrode (CNE) where the core and outer tube serve as electrodes. Tissue impedance was measured using 9 excitation frequencies between 20 kHz and 100 kHz, capturing the resistive and reactive components. Calibration was conducted before every series of measurements by immersing a new CNE in a saline solution of known concentration. EBI measurements on the tissues were performed within 15 minutes of sample resection to ensure the tissue's integrity. The practitioner performed repeated measurements (using a dedicated user interface) by positioning the CNE onto different areas of the specimen, including frankly tumor regions and peripheral areas visually assessed as healthy tissue by the expert

clinician collecting the data. Each EBI measurement was then matched with the histopathology results to confirm the tissue label (i.e., "Pathologic Tissue" if at least in situ carcinoma or "Healthy Tissue").

The acquired signals were originally contained in 215 text files. Data were reviewed in a first analysis phase, considering the notes provided by the clinician during the measurement procedures. Based on these annotations, entries affected by measurement errors were excluded, resulting in a refined dataset of 70 files. This final set was then used to compute the magnitude and phase of the tissue impedance. Subsequently, data were analyzed to identify significant differences in EBI parameters between healthy and cancerous tissue samples.

Data normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, and statistical comparisons were performed with the Kruskal-Wallis test. To explore automated cancer detection from EBI signals, different classifiers were built and trained to distinguish malignant versus healthy tissues. To assess model performance, a Leave-One-Out cross-validation was implemented, excluding one complete acquisition (measurements at all 9 frequency points) at each iteration. Additional patient-specific classifiers were examined to assess personalized diagnostic potential. MATLAB 2024b and Python 3.13.3 were utilized for the whole software development.

RESULTS

The dataset was first analyzed in a general manner, followed by a stratified analysis based on tumor stage and, subsequently, on an individual patient basis.

The distribution and frequency response of healthy and pathologic tissue's signals (respectively plotted in green and red) are shown in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2**.

Figure 1. General larynx data: Nyquist plots with 2D error bars summarizing all the data included in the analysis (the mean and std of resistance and reactance are shown for each frequency).

Figure 2. General larynx data: electrical properties for all the data included in the analysis (the mean and std of resistance and reactance are shown for each frequency).

An initial overview revealed distinct electrical properties across samples resected from different laryngeal regions that were consistent in both healthy and cancerous samples, indicating a strong link between electrical characteristics and tissue functional composition.

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in the electrical properties between healthy and pathological tissues, with highly significant p-values ($p \ll 0.05$) observed for magnitude and reactance. The results, in terms of signal distribution and statistical significance, remained consistent across all frequency points and at the individual level, reinforcing the robustness of the overall findings and providing a foundation for a personalized approach, considering subject-specific variations.

The best performance in the discrimination of pathologic and healthy tissues was achieved by the *cubic SVM* model (Accuracy = 99.7%, Sensitivity = 99.6%, Specificity = 99.7%) trained on all the available data.

Tumor stage recognition was also explored. As an initial approach, based upon the clinicians' annotations, the dataset was partitioned into two subsets referred to as "early-stage pathology" or "advanced pathology", respectively assigned to stages 1-2 and 3-4. The newly built and trained classifiers yielded highly satisfactory results, with the *Wide Neural Network* model achieving the highest performance (Accuracy = 96.9%, Sensitivity = 98.2%, Specificity = 95.2%).

Finally, given the intended clinical application, anomaly detection was explored as a viable strategy for identifying pathological tissues using a personalized approach. Several one-class classification models were explored using only healthy signals acquired from the same patient for training. The best performances were achieved building a threshold-based classifier using the *Typicality coefficient* (Accuracy = 94.1%, Sensitivity = 88.2%, Specificity = 100.0%) and the scikit-learn *One-class SVM* (Accuracy = 97.0%, Sensitivity = 94.1%, Specificity = 100.0%).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to provide an in-depth characterization of bioimpedance signals measured on healthy and cancerous laryngeal tissue samples, to better understand how these data can be effectively utilized in diagnostics.

In the discrimination of tissue status, pathological samples consistently exhibited higher resistance compared to healthy ones, an observation that aligns with typical histopathological features of SCC, including the development of stiff plaques and keratinization [7]. Moreover, impedance values were generally lower in cancerous tissues across all anatomical regions, reflecting structural alterations at the cellular and extracellular levels. Reactance was also found to be significantly reduced in pathological tissues: this supports the notion that tumor progression is associated with increased cellular damage and loss of membrane functionality and integrity [8]. Additionally, specific patterns within the pathological samples were detected, enabling a correct classification of tumor risk levels. These promising findings confirm the strong potential of EBI as a diagnostic tool for early tumor detection, also introducing a patient-specific diagnostic algorithm.

Future research will explore the feasibility of using single-frequency measurements for classification tasks, which could simplify data acquisition and processing and allow real-time application in a clinical setting. Additionally, future developments will include training optimized classifiers and integrating them into specially adapted sensing instruments to complement traditional medical instruments, promoting less invasive diagnostic procedures and EBI's applicability in intraoperative tissue discrimination and preservation tasks.

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